

The Reaction between Quinolinic Anhydride and Phenylhydrazine.

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Hötte (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1887, ii, 35, 265, *et seq*) has shown that phthalic anhydride condenses with phenylhydrazine to give four different condensation products under different experimental conditions.

Phthalylphenylhydrazine.

Anilidophthalaminic acid.

Phthalyl diphenylhydrazine
(Dianilinophthalyl diamide).

β -Phthalylphenylhydrazine.

According to Hötte (*loc. cit.*) the compound of type (IV) is formed not by the direct action of one molecule of phenylhydrazine and one molecule of phthalic anhydride but by the elimination of one molecule of phenylhydrazine from a compound of the type (III) first formed.

Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1103) attempted the condensation of quinolinic acid with phenylhydrazine and obtained a compound of the type (I).

Using different experimental conditions, besides quinolinyl-phenylhydrazine, compounds of the types (II) and (III) in a very pure condition and most probably a compound of the type (IV) in a somewhat impure condition have now been obtained by the condensation of quinolinic anhydride with phenylhydrazine. In an experiment in which quinolinic acid and higher temperature were used, a new compound, as indicated by its melting point, containing

the same percentage of nitrogen as required by the compound of type (III) was obtained. In view of the fact that at a higher temperature quinolinic acid evolves carbon dioxide and is converted to nicotinic acid it is surmised that the same change took place under conditions of the experiment and the resulting nicotinic acid reacted with phenylhydrazine to form phenylhydrazinonicotinate.

Quinolinic as well as phthalic and naphthalic anhydrides have also been condensed with unsymmetrical methylphenylhydrazine but in each case compounds of the type (I) have only been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Anilidoquinolinaminic Acid.

Quinolinic anhydride (0.75 g.) was suspended in benzene (10 c.c.) and to this, a solution of phenylhydrazine (0.55 g.) in 5 c.c. of benzene added and the mixture allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature with occasional stirring for 2 days. The separated solid was collected, washed first with benzene, then with a little alcohol and finally crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 146° (decomp.). It is insoluble in benzene, easily soluble in alcohol or acetic acid. It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution. (Found: N, 16.68. $C_{13}H_{11}O_3N_3$ requires N, 16.34 per cent.)

Quinolinyl diphenylhydrazine (Dianilidoquinolinyl diamide).

A mixture of quinolinic anhydride (0.7 g.) and phenylhydrazine (0.5 g.) (equimolecular quantities) was heated in a test tube on an oil-bath at 120-30° for 10 minutes and then allowed to cool. The fused mass was dissolved in alcohol. On adding very dilute hydrochloric acid to the solution, a solid separated which crystallised from

alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 201°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid or pyridine, and insoluble in benzene. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with light violet colour which disappears on heating. (Found: N, 20·31. $C_{19}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 20·17 per cent.).

In the anticipation of obtaining β quinolinylphenylhydrazine (*i.e.*, compound of the type, IV), the preceding compound was heated to 200° for 1 hour. It suffered decomposition and phenylhydrazine was given out. But the other resulting product could not be obtained in a sufficiently pure state.

Phenylhydrazinonicotinate.

Quinolinic acid (0·5 g.) with phenylhydrazine (2 c.c.) was heated in a test tube on the oil-bath for 20 minutes at 200-30°. On adding spirit to the resulting product, a yellow compound separated which crystallised from alcohol as yellow plates, m.p. 185°. It is sparingly soluble in cold alcohol, more so in the hot solvent and insoluble in benzene. (Found: N, 20·24. $C_{12}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 19·71 per cent.).

Phthalyl- α -methylphenylhydrazine.

The fused mass obtained by heating together methylphenylhydrazine (0·6 g.) and phthalic anhydride (0·7 g.) on an oil-bath at 130° for 10 minutes, was dissolved in alcohol. The crystalline precipitate which separated on the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid to the solution, was finally crystallised from alcohol in yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 124°. It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid or acetone, and insoluble in benzene or ether. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a pink colour. (Found: N, 11·37. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11·11 per cent.).

Quinolinyl- α -methylphenylhydrazine.— Methylphenylhydrazine (0.6 g.) and quinolinic anhydride (0.7 g.) were heated together at 120° for 15 minutes on the oil-bath. The resulting mass was dissolved in alcohol and precipitated from the solution by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from alcohol as yellow prisms, m.p. 155°. Its properties are similar to those of the preceding compound. (Found: N, 16.82. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 16.60 per cent.).

Nphthalyl- α -methylphenylhydrazine was prepared from naphthalic anhydride (1 g.) and methylphenylhydrazine (0.6 g.) in the same way as the two preceding compounds and finally obtained as yellow plates, m.p. 210°. It is soluble in alcohol or acetic acid, more so in the hot solvents and insoluble in benzene. (Found: N, 9.58. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent.).

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